

WEAR PROPERTIES OF PAN- AND PITCH-BASED CARBON FIBER REINFORCED PLASTICS WITH SiC-NANOPARTICLES

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ABSTRACT

Light-weighting is one of the key technologies to solve the energy and environment issues. Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) show great potential for light-weight application in structural components, and it have become a dominant material in the aerospace and automotive industries. However, It is necessary to consider the only in highly specialized situations and several types of requirements due to expand the application fields. To apply the CFRP in sliding members such as gears and shafts, it is necessary to reinforce the surfaces. The purpose of this study was to improve the wear resistance of surface for the CFRP. Friction test was conducted to examine the wear properties of CFRP with SiC-nanoparticles.

Wear resistances of K13C/EX-1515 and QC133-149A were improved by the addition of nanoparticles, but no large enhancement of wear resistance was observed in M60J/EX-1515. In order to confirm the wear process, the friction test was performed by changing the number of round trips. In K13C/EX-1515, the specific wear rate increased rapidly after a certain number of round trips. In M60J/EX-1515, the specific wear rate increased linearly. In QC133-149A at 0 vol%, the specific wear rate was increased linearly. In QC133-149A at 1.0 and 2.5 vol%, the specific wear rate increased with a certain number of round trips.

In K13C/EX-1515, cracks occurred at the carbon fiber/resin interface and inside the carbon fiber. When nanoparticles were added, there were no cracks at the interface or destruction of carbon fibers. In M60J/EX-1515, cracks of the carbon fiber/resin interface and the peeling of the carbon fiber were confirmed with a small number of round trips. In QC133-149A, the surface was worn first and cracks were occurred at the carbon fiber/resin interface as the number of round trips increased. When the nanoparticles were added, the surface wear was suppressed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Light-weighting is one of the key technologies to solve the energy and environment issues. Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) show great potential for light-weight application in structural components, and it have become a dominant material in the aerospace and automotive industries. However, It is necessary to consider the only in highly specialized situations and several types of requirements due to expand the application fields. To apply the CFRP in sliding members such as gears and shafts, it is necessary to reinforce the surfaces because the surfaces of CFRP have resin layer. Wang et al. have discussed the wear properties of a polymer and proposed an enhancement of wear resistance by adding nanoparticles [1]. By adding SiC-nanoparticle in a CFRP to form hybrid composites may create materials possessing the enhancement of wear resistance of the CFRP.

In the present work, friction and wear properties of high modulus pitch-based, high modulus polyacrylonitrile (PAN)-based, and high strength PAN-based CFRP with SiC-nanoparticles were investigated.

2 MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Material

The three types of CFRP prepreg with high modulus pitch-based carbon fiber reinforced plastics (K13C/EX-1515) (fiber: K13C, matrix: EX-1515, nominal volume fraction of fiber (V_f): 53.1 %), high modulus PAN-based carbon fiber reinforced plastics (M60J/EX-1515) (fiber: M60J, matrix: EX-1515, V_f : 54.1 %), and high strengths PAN-based carbon fiber reinforced plastics (QC133-149A) (fiber: IM600, matrix: #133, V_f : 56.7 %) were used.

The 130 nm β -SiC-nanoparticle (average particle diameter: 130 nm, density: 3.22 g/cm³) was used as reinforcement.

2.2 Material preparation

The prepreps were cut into the appropriate size and fiber orientation (lengthwise 300 mm - crosswise 150 mm (fiber direction is lengthwise direction)). Appropriate amounts of SiC-nanoparticle were added into outermost of surface. Two different volume fractions 1.0, 2.5 vol% of SiC-nanoparticles filled and unfilled (0 vol%) were prepared.

Fiber orientation and layers of the composites were set to [0]_s. The prepreps were pressed in 0.49 MPa and cured in 180 °C for 4 h (heating rate was 1 °C/min) by an autoclave.

2.3 Friction and wear test

Friction and wear test were performed in parallel with the fiber direction using the ball-on-disk type friction tester (FRP 2100). Ball material is SUJ-2 (bearing steel abrasion ball, spherical diameter: 4.76 mm). Ball was cleaned by acetone. The specimens were cleaned by hexane, then they were kept for more than 24 hours in the laboratory environment at room temperature. The test conditions were following: the load of 2.5, 5 N, sliding width of 10 mm, linear velocity of 40 mm/s, number of round trips of 1500 times.

After the test, wear tracks were observed using a laser microscope (Keyence VK-210) to calculate the specific wear rate. For calculating the specific wear rate, the following equation was used. w_s : specific wear rate, S_{mean} : average damage area, F : load.

$$w_s = S_{mean}/F \text{ } [\mu\text{m}^3/\text{Nm}] \quad (1)$$

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Observation of the samples

The produced sample cross section was observed by SEM. Fig.1 shows a cross-sectional view near the sample surface. It was found that the nanoparticle layer was present on the sample surface by the addition of nanoparticles. The nanoparticle layer became thicker as the addition amount increased. It was also found that PAN-based CFRP (M60J, IM600) were smaller in diameter of fibers and larger in number of fibers than pitch-based CFRP (K13C).

Figure 1: Cross-sectional view of CFRP surface

3.2 Friction and wear test

Fig.2 shows the results of the friction test. In K13C/EX-1515 and QC133-149A, wear resistances were improved by the addition of nanoparticles. The maximum of the wear resistance was observed for the 1.0 vol% SiC-nanoparticles filled CFRP. However, no large enhancement of wear resistance was observed in M60J/EX1515.

Figure 2: Results of friction and wear test

3.3 Wear process

The effect of number of round trips on the wear resistance was examined to clarify the wear process of the SiC-nanoparticles filled and unfilled CFRP. The load of 5 N and number of round trips of 100, 250, 500, 1000, and 1500 times were used. The results are shown in Fig.3. In K13C/EX-1515, the specific wear rate didn't change until 1000 times, and it was found that the specific wear rate rapidly increased from 1000 to 1500 times. By the addition of nanoparticles, enhancement in wear resistance was confirmed at 1.0 vol%, but there was no change at 2.5 vol%. In M60J/EX-1515, it was found that the specific wear rate increases linearly. It didn't change even when nanoparticles were added. In QC133-149A, the specific wear rate increased linearly at 0 vol%. By the addition of nanoparticles, the specific wear rate didn't change until 1000 times, and it was found that the specific wear rate increased from 1000 times to 1500 times.

(b) M60J/EX-1515

(c) QC133-149A

Figure 3: Specific wear rate with varying number of round trips (5 N)

3.4 Wear cross section

The wear cross section was observed at each number of round trips. The wear cross sections are shown in Fig.4-6.

In K13C/EX-1515 at 0 vol%, the cracks had already occurred inside the carbon fiber at 100 times. After that, the carbon fiber was broken at 1000 times without peeling, and the cracks progressed. The peeling of carbon fiber occurred more than a certain number of round trips, so it can be inferred that the fatigue caused by the repeated load was the cause. In addition, it is thought that energy was dissipated by the destruction of the carbon fiber. At 1.0 vol%, the cracks at the carbon fiber/resin interface and inside of the carbon fiber and destruction of the carbon fiber were not confirmed at all up to 1000 times. Therefore, it is thought that it was broken and peeled off between 1000 and 1500 times. At 2.5 vol%, the cracks had formed at the nanoparticles layer/carbon fiber interface. The wear process was similar to that at 0 vol% (Fig.4).

In M60J/EX-1515, the cracks at the carbon fiber/resin interface and peeling of carbon fiber were simultaneously confirmed with a small number of round trips under all conditions. There was no energy dissipation because the carbon fiber was not destroyed. It is thought that the force is easily transmitted to the inside because of the dense distribution of carbon fibers. In addition, the peeling occurred immediately and the nanoparticles layer on the surface disappeared. Therefore, it is considered that the specific wear rate was almost same (Fig.5).

In QC133-149A at 0 vol%, the surface was worn at 100 times. After that, the surface wear progressed at 1000 times, and it was confirmed that cracks occurred at the carbon fiber/resin interface. At 1.0, 2.5 vol%, the surface wear was not observed during a small number of round trips. In addition, it was found that the surface was worn a little and that a large crack was occurred at the carbon fiber/resin interface at 1000 times (Fig.6).

Figure 4: Cross sections of wear tracks with varying number of round trips (K13C/EX-1515)

Figure 5: Cross sections of wear tracks with varying number of round trips (M60J/EX-1515)

Figure 6: Cross sections of wear tracks with varying number of round trips (QC133-149A)

4 CONCLUSIONS

In the present work, friction tests and SEM observations were conducted to investigate the wear characteristics of PAN- and pitch-based carbon fiber reinforced plastics with SiC-nanoparticles. The obtained results are shown below.

- (1) In K13C/EX-1515, the wear resistance was improved by the addition of SiC-nanoparticles. The specific wear rate did not increase up to a certain number of round trips. The cracks were occurred at the interface and inside the carbon fiber, and the carbon fiber was broken.
- (2) In M60J/EX-1515, there was no large enhancement of wear resistance even when adding SiC-nanoparticles. The specific wear rate increased linearly. No destruction of the carbon fiber was observed. In addition, the cracks were occurred at the interface with a small number of round trips, and peeling occurred.
- (3) In QC133-149A, the wear resistance was improved by the addition of SiC-nanoparticles. The specific wear rate increased linearly. The cracks at the interface did not immediately occur and only the surface was worn.

REFERENCES

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